

HISTORICAL DEVELOPMENT AND PROSPECTS OF TECHNOLOGY EDUCATION IN GENERAL SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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Annotation:

This article analyzes the formation, stages of development, and current state of technology education in general secondary schools. It explains how the subject initially emerged as labor education and gradually evolved by integrating modern technologies. The article also discusses current challenges and future prospects of the subject. The importance of improving technological education to develop students' practical and vocational skills is emphasized.

Keywords:

technology education, labor education, historical development, education system, innovation, practical skills, vocational training, curriculum, modern technologies, prospects

Introduction:

Today, increasing attention is being paid to technology education in the education system. This subject plays an important role in developing students' practical skills. Initially, technology education appeared as labor education aimed at teaching basic manual work skills. Over time, with the development of science and technology, the content of this subject has significantly expanded. Today, it includes not only simple labor activities but also modern production, design, and innovative processes.

Main Part:

The historical development of technology education can be divided into several stages. At the initial stage, it focused on manual labor and basic craftsmanship skills. At the next stage, with the development of industry, the subject expanded to include knowledge about technical devices, mechanisms, and production processes.

At the present stage, technology education is closely connected with information technologies, robotics, design, and modeling. This contributes to the development of students' creativity and innovative thinking. However, some problems still exist, such as inadequacy of modern equipment in schools, insufficient teacher qualifications, and the need to regularly update curricula. In the future, it is necessary to introduce modern technologies, apply STEAM approaches, and develop students' independent thinking skills.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, technology education has undergone a long historical development and has become an important part of the education system. It helps students gain practical skills and prepare for future professions. By solving existing problems and introducing modern approaches, the effectiveness of this subject can be further improved. In the future, it will play a key role in training competitive specialists.

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